

Application of Customer Relationship Management Systems in Business: Challenges and Opportunities

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Abstract : Customer relationship management (CRM) systems in business are a reality of the contemporary business world for the last decade or so. Still, there are grey areas regarding the successful implementation and operation of CRM systems in business. This paper, through the systematic study of the CRM implementation paradigm, attempts to identify the most important challenges and opportunities that the CRM systems face in a rapidly changing business world.

Keywords : customer relationship management, CRM, business, literature review

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